

Indicators to Measure the Influence of Celebrity Personality and Humor Ads on Consumer Purchasing Intentions

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ABSTRACT: Humorous advertising is considered the most effective marketing tool. However, on the other hand, consumers still identify the credibility of celebrities who star in advertisements. Companies need to determine which aspects of these two things are effective in increasing consumer purchasing intentions according to the type of product and target market. Apart from that, this research also measures endorsed brand credibility, transfer of brand image, attitude toward ads and e-word of mouth. This measuring tool was tested on a sample of 30 women who had seen a funny endorsement video from a famous comedian digital in Indonesia. The data was processed using IBM SPSS Statistics 26. The test results showed that the measuring instrument consisting of 7 constructs and 49 items met the validity and reliability criteria. Therefore, this particular measurement instrument was prepared for use in further research purposes.

KEYWORDS: Celebrity Endorser, Brand Credibility, Brand Image, e-WOM, Humorous Ads, Purchase Intention

INTRODUCTION

The Royal Islamic Strategic Studies Centre (RISSC) report for the 2023 edition reveals that the Muslim population in Indonesia has reached 237,55 million, equivalent to 86,7% of the total population (Annur, 2023). The growth of the Muslim fashion trend is driven by the awareness of Muslims regarding Islamic dress codes and the diverse styles influenced by fashion and technology developments (Anafarhanah, 2019). Sales of Muslim fashion have increased, making Indonesia the third-largest consumer of Muslim fashion globally with a total expenditure of 20 billion USD (Nabilah, 2022). The Muslim fashion industry in Indonesia has significant opportunities, fueled by consumer support for local products. Social media, particularly Instagram, has become an effective marketing channel with an active user base of 167 million people (We Are Social, 2023). Technology has transformed shopping behaviors, but the need for reliable information remains high. Celebrity endorsements, such as those done by Fadil Jaidi (an Indonesian comedian digital), are an effective marketing strategy. Endorsement content that incorporates humor successfully captures audience attention, increases sales, and shapes a positive image for the endorsed brand (Gityandra, 2020). This research aims to evaluate the validity and reliability of the constructs such as digital comedian personality, humorous ads, endorsed brand credibility, transfer of brand image, attitude toward ads, e-word of mouth, and consumer purchasing intention.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The section discusses the role of celebrity personality in strategic brand promotion, emphasizing that celebrities not only endorse but also play a crucial role in designing, positioning, and selling products and services. The credibility of a celebrity as a source is essential for message acceptance, with factors such as expertise, trustworthiness, and likeability identified by Kotler & Keller (2016). Rai et al. (2021) add five factors: celebrity expertise level, celebrity attractiveness, celebrity trustworthiness, celebrity likeability, and celebrity character. A survey on comedian by Sokanu Interactive Inc. (2023) reveals characteristics such as creativity, originality, expressiveness, enterprising nature, social responsibility, and agreeableness. The review also introduces the Big Five Personality Traits Model for comedian, including openness to experience, conscientiousness, extraversion, agreeableness, and neuroticism. Additionally, it explores the importance of celebrity endorsement credibility, focusing on convincing, believable, and attractiveness dimensions. The transfer of brand image is discussed as the process of associating a celebrity's image with a brand's image, influenced by image-based similarity and image congruency. Finally, humorous ads are examined, highlighting their appeal in transformational appeals and viral marketing. However, it's noted that while humor is effective, it should not overshadow the brand message and needs careful execution to avoid risks and meet audience expectations.

On the other hand, the effectiveness of humorous appeals in influencing attitudes, emphasizing the need for humor to stay focused on the brand or main value for maximum effectiveness. Comparative advertising yields varied results, being most effective for unknown brands with strong functional advantages. The decision to use expressive or utilitarian appeals depends on whether the brand fulfills expressive or utilitarian needs. Attitudes are measured on a semantic differential scale with four items: pleasant, good, likeable, and interesting. The concept of congruity is introduced, highlighting that positive or negative attitudes toward both the source (celebrity) and the message contribute to congruence. Consumer attitudes can shift, leading to an increased alignment between evaluations of the celebrity and the brand. The principle of congruity suggests that communicators can use their positive image to mitigate negative perceptions of a brand but may lose some audience appreciation in the process. This is helped by e-word of mouth, emphasizing its impact on individual purchase attitudes, especially with the prevalence of the internet. Small businesses with limited median budgets find e-WOM crucial for positive word of mouth promotion. Consumers tend to generate positive word of mouth and share information about their positive consumption experiences, influencing group communication and acting as a primary source of product information. The ultimate goal of this research is to improve consumer purchase intention. It is defined as self-directed instructions to buy a product, influenced by promotions and attractive offers. Purchase intention is linked to the concepts of liking a product, believing in its utility, and forming preferences during the evaluation stage. Two common factors, attitudes of others and situational factors, intervene between purchase intention and the final purchase decision, with the influence of others and unexpected situational factors impacting the alignment of purchase intentions.

This research draws upon the work of Al-Gasawneh & Al-Adamat, (2020); Audi et al., (2015); Nuseir, (2019); Primanto & Dharmmesta, (2019); Rai et al., (2021). Research of Rai et al. (2021) finds that sports celebrity personality has positive and significant impact on endorsed brand credibility and transfer of brand image, then those variables influence the consumer purchasing intention. On the other hand, McCracken (1989) in Audi et al. (2015) shows how consumers associate implications with celebrities, which are then transferred to the brands. The model involves three sequential stages where meaning associated with celebrities is transferred to brands. Apart from the celebrity personality, there is the humorous ads variable as an independent variable. According to Primanto & Dharmmesta (2019), humorous ads has positive relationship with attitude toward ads then e-word of mouth. Nuseir (2019) added that e-word of mouth has positive impact on consumer purchase intention. While Al-Gasawneh & Al-Adamat (2020) explained that attitude toward ads can have positive impact on consumer purchasing intention through e-word of mouth. Based on this explanation, a conceptual framework for this research was formed as follows:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

MEASUREMENT MODEL

All statements in the questionnaire can be said to be valid and reliable after carrying out the three methodological stages (Indrawati, 2015). First, the researcher conducted a validity test to measure how well the research variable items could be accepted rationally through the results of modifications to the questionnaire items from previous research conducted by Primanto & Dharmmesta (2019); Rai et al. (2021). Second, the author asked for the opinions of experts who have expertise in the field of advertising marketing as input or suggestions in improving the questionnaire items. In the third stage, the clarity of the questionnaire can be ensured by carrying out readability tests on individual samples. This phase seeks to identify and correct potential sources of ambiguity or confusion. Table 1 shows the results of previous test questions before the start of the trial.

Table 1. Questionnaire Items

<i>Item Code</i>	<i>Items on Comedian Personality</i>
CEL1	(name of comedian celebrity) has excellent comedy skills
CEL2	(name of comedian celebrity) is expressive when he jokes
CEL3	(name of comedian celebrity) is very interactive when clowning around as a team
CEL4	(name of comedian celebrity) is a very talented comedian
CEL5	(name of comedian celebrity) is very creative in comedy
CEL6	(name of comedian celebrity) is goal oriented
CEL7	(name of comedian celebrity) is a hard worker
CEL8	(name of comedian celebrity) has a high level of comedy ability
CA1	(name of comedian celebrity) has a lot of media attention
CA2	(name of comedian celebrity) is a recognizable
CA3	(name of comedian celebrity) is physically fit
CA4	(name of comedian celebrity) is out going
CA5	(name of comedian celebrity) is energetic
CA6	(name of comedian celebrity) is distinctive
CA7	(name of comedian celebrity) is funny
CA8	(name of comedian celebrity) is entertaining while joking
CT1	(name of comedian celebrity) is responsible
CT2	(name of comedian celebrity) is well spoken
CT3	(name of comedian celebrity) is intelligent

CT4	(name of comedian celebrity) shows good linguistic skills in comedy
CL1	(name of comedian celebrity) is modest
CL2	(name of comedian celebrity) is honest
CL3	(name of comedian celebrity) is kind
CL4	(name of comedian celebrity) is likeable
CC1	(name of comedian celebrity) is a cheering comedian
CC2	(name of comedian celebrity) is down to earth
CC3	(name of comedian celebrity) is a unique comedian
Item Code	Items on Humorous Ads
HA1	The advertising message starring (name of comedian celebrity) is fun to watch
HA2	(name of comedian celebrity) videos are really fun to watch
HA3	(name of comedian celebrity) is very funny
HA4	I find the product advertisement endorsed by (name of comedian celebrity) very funny
Item Code	Items on Endorsed Brand Credibility
EBC1	I feel confident in the product brand endorsed by (name of comedian celebrity)
EBC2	I feel that the product brand endorsed by (name of comedian celebrity) is trustworthy
EBC3	I feel that the product brand endorsed by (name of comedian celebrity) looks classy
Item Code	Items on Transfer of Brand Image
TBI1	(name of comedian celebrity) and (name of the endorsed brand) have a similar image
TBI2	The image I associate with (name of endorsed brand) is related to the image I associate with (name of comedian celebrity)
TBI3	My image of (name of endorsed brand) is consistent with my image of (name of comedian celebrity)
Item Code	Items on Attitude toward Ads
ATA1	I find the product advertisements endorsed by (name of comedian celebrity) interesting
ATA2	I find the product advertisements endorsed by (name of comedian celebrity) enjoyable
ATA3	I like product advertisements endorsed by (name of comedian celebrity)
ATA4	I find the product advertisements endorsed by (name of comedian celebrity) are not bad

<i>Item Code</i>	<i>Items on e-Word of Mouth</i>
EWOM1	I recommend product advertisements endorsed by (name of comedian celebrity) to friends
EWOM2	I told my friend about funny product advertisement endorsed by (name of comedian celebrity)
EWOM3	I will click “share” to show my appreciation for product advertisements endorsed by (name of comedian celebrity) on social media
EWOM4	I told my friend about (name of endorsed brand) endorsed by (name of comedian celebrity)
<i>Item Code</i>	<i>Items on Consumer Purchase Intention</i>
CPI1	I want to buy the advertised brand/product in the near future
CPI2	I may buy the advertised brand/product in the near future
CPI3	I definitely will buy the advertised brand/product in the near future
CPI4	I probably will buy the advertised brand/product in the near future

Source: Primary data processed

METHOD AND RESULT

Researchers conducted trials to improve the quality of the questionnaire. In addition, the trial aims to ensure the validity and reliability of the instrument scores by involving 30 respondents for initial data collection. The validity test in this study used the Critical Item-Total Correlation (CITC) metric rule, which exceeded the threshold of 0,361. In the context of reliability testing, what is usually used is Cronbach’s Alpha, which is said to be reliable if it exceeds the Cronbach’s Alpha. The Cronbach’s Alpha score of 0,60 (Sugiyono, 2019). In summary, the test results are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Pilot Test Result

<i>CP Code</i>	<i>CITC</i>	<i>Cronbach’s Alpha</i>
CEL1	0,572	0,778
CEL2	0,527	
CEL3	0,489	
CEL4	0,665	
CEL5	0,390	
CEL6	0,537	
CEL7	0,477	
CEL8	0,510	
CA1	0,486	0,821
CA2	0,586	
CA3	0,486	
CA4	0,830	

CA5	0,646	
CA6	0,748	
CA7	0,566	
CA8	0,716	
CT1	0,461	0,758
CT2	0,654	
CT3	0,568	
CT4	0,565	
CL1	0,390	0,673
CL2	0,520	
CL3	0,535	
CL4	0,443	
CC1	0,607	0,784
CC2	0,556	
CC3	0,713	
HA Code	CITC	Cronbach's Alpha
HA1	0,744	0,892
HA2	0,898	
HA3	0,610	
HA4	0,810	
EBC Code	CITC	Cronbach's Alpha
EBC1	0,796	0,851
EBC2	0,739	
EBC3	0,651	
TBI Code	CITC	Cronbach's Alpha
TBI1	0,783	0,849
TBI2	0,788	
TBI3	0,592	
ATA Code	CITC	Cronbach's Alpha
ATA1	0,891	0,932

ATA2	0,818	
ATA3	0,920	
ATA4	0,779	
EWOM Code	CITC	Cronbach's Alpha
EWOM1	0,847	0,925
EWOM2	0,862	
EWOM3	0,842	
EWOM4	0,801	
CPI Code	CITC	Cronbach's Alpha
CPI1	0,897	0,950
CPI2	0,803	
CPI3	0,916	
CPI4	0,925	

Source: Primary data processed

Based on the results of the validity test using Corrected Item-Total Correlation (CITC), all statement items in this research questionnaire were more than 0,361, which means all items were said to be valid. Meanwhile, the reliability test using Cronbach's Alpha is more than 0,60, which means all constructs are valid and acceptable.

CONCLUSION

This research conducted a pilot test with a sample size of 30 respondents. The criteria for respondents include being Indonesian Muslim women who have seen Fadil Jaidi's endorsement video wearing Muslim women's clothing. The findings of this trial demonstrate the validity and reliability of the measuring material consisting of 49 statement items used in this research. Therefore, suggested measurement materials are prepared for use in further research.

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